

Peripheral arterial disease as a present health threat

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Abstract

Current predictions indicate that increased life expectancy in peripheral arterial disease in the developed country, including Poland, has been observed. Many risk factors cause morbidity to increase drastically. This includes overweight, smoking or hypertension. Symptoms are very different, they may also not occur, so correct diagnosis is sometimes difficult. It is important to know the patient's own health and prevention. Peripheral arterial disease is a chronic disease that will accompany the patient for the rest of their life, so it is important to emphasize how important healthy habits are, including proper nutrition and physical activity, to prevent illness.

Keywords:

Introduction

Due to the prolonged lifespan observed in developed countries, the occurrence of peripheral arterial disease is expected to increase. It currently accounts for 12% -14% of the general population, up to 20% for patients over 75 years of age. It is a symptomatic disease but can also occur asymptotically [1, 2]. There are many factors by which the risk of morbidity increases dramatically. These include smoking, overweight or hypertension. In the case of peripheral arterial disease, intermittent claudication often occurs, which is manifested by pain, most often located in the calves, limiting the motor activity of the patient, which in turn leads to deterioration of the condition [3]. Diagnosis is based on the measurement of the ankle-brachial index, and often a functional test on a treadmill is used. The most commonly used classification tool is the Fontaine's Scale and the Rutherford-Baker Classification. It is estimated that 7% of patients will

undergo lower limb amputation, 4% will require amputation, and 16% will have worsening of the disease [4]. In recent years, the incidence of chronic diseases has increased, and special attention has been paid not only to the physical but also psychological issues that occur in a given disease. The psychological burden of a patient, which results, among other things, from reduced physical capacity, leads to the avoidance of daily activities and to the realization of social roles due to physical limitations [5]. Numerous reports have confirmed the occurrence of psychopathology in the course of chronic diseases [5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. The present study presents the threat posed by peripheral arterial disease, the ways in which it is diagnosed, and the physical training used to improve health.

1. Peripheral artery disease

PAD is defined as obstructive arterial disease of the lower limbs which reduces arterial blood flow to the

Figure 1. Occurrence of intermittent claudication in large population studies [3].

lower limbs during physical activity or at rest in the case of advanced stage. The PAD is diverse and may manifest as an asymptomatic arterial disease with abnormal non-invasive tests, symptomatic disease with classical or non-typical acute claudication or critical limb ischaemia (CLI) [1].

2. Epidemiology

Peripheral arterial disease affects 12% - 14% of the general population and its incidence increases with age, affecting 20% of patients over 75 years of age [2]. Occurrence of intermittent claudication is shown in Figure 1. Data from the Atherosclerosis Registry for Continued Health presented at the annual American College of Cardiology show that among 7013 patients with symptomatic PAD, 63% of patients with multivessel disease [10]. In a study by E. Rossi, 51 patients with symptomatic PAD were observed for 24 months. 17 patients (34%) had myocardial infarction, and 11 patients died [11].

Extension of life expectancy, which is currently observed in the society of developed countries, results in a higher prevalence of PAD.

3. Etiopathogenesis

Peripheral arterial disease is caused by atherosclerosis, which leads to narrowing and closure of the major vessels that supply the lower limbs in the blood. Atherosclerosis is a chronic inflammatory process that takes place in blood vessels. In the space between the endothelium and the muscular layer of the vessel there are deposits, which include macrophages, low-density lipoprotein (LDL), foam cells and extracellular cholesterol. The so-called "fatty bands" are the earliest forms of atherosclerotic lesions.

Over time, the "fatty" elements attach the fibrous parts of the connective tissue which, as a result of the overgrowth and surrounding of the primary inflammatory flares, lead to its separation from the vessel. The advanced form of atherosclerosis thus defined is defined as "atherosclerotic plaque". It can accumulate in the lumen of the vessel, narrowing it and restricting blood flow [12]. In patients with atherosclerosis is not advanced, the blood flow in the lower limbs is normal at rest (hence no symptoms). During exercise, the narrowed or closed arteries restrict the flow of blood to the muscles of the limbs, resulting in an inadequate metabolic demand and the supply of oxygen leading to the onset of claudication [3].

4. Risk factors

Although the risk factors described below are generally referred to as risk factors for development, there are in many cases evidence of their association with the disease. Non-modifiable factors and lifestyle factors may increase the likelihood of arterial atherosclerosis (Tab.1).

Each of the above factors is a potential risk of developing the disease, so it is very important to minimize their impact by altering your current lifestyle (diet, physical activity, stress) and pharmacological treatment (normalization of hypertension, cholesterol reduction). Analysts at the American Academy of Science stress that the lifestyle of a person has the highest (more than 50%) impact on an objective sense of health or disease. A man should be aware that he has the ability to influence the nature of the surrounding environment, which reduces the impact of

Table 1. Risk factors.

Risk factors	
Race	Non-white race is a risk factor for the development of the PAD. Belonging to the black race increases the risk of PAD more than 2 times [13].
Sex	Symptoms and asymptomatic PAD are more common in men than in women, especially in younger age groups. In patients with intermittent claudication, the ratio between men and women ranges from 1: 1 to 2: 1 [3].
Age	Significant increase in both morbidity and mortality with PAD with age [3].
Smoking	Termination is 2-5 times more common in people who smoke than non-smokers [14]. In smokers, the PAD appears to be about 10 years earlier than non-smokers. There is a 4-times higher risk of developing chronic claudication compared to non-smokers [15].
Diabetes	Termination is approximately twice as common in diabetic patients than in non-diabetic subjects. The American Diabetes Association (ADA) recommends screening for PAD using ABI every 5 years in patients with diabetes [16].
Hypertension	Hypertension is associated with the development of various cardiovascular diseases, including the PAD. However, the relative risk of developing PAD is lower in patients with hypertension than in patients with diabetes and smoking [3].
Dyslipidemia	Fasting cholesterol > 7 mmol / l (270 mg / dl) was associated with a 2-fold increased incidence of intermittent claudication [17].
Inflammation markers	Studies show that C-reactive protein (CRP) levels were elevated in asymptomatic patients who developed PAD over the next 5 years compared with age-matched control who remained asymptomatic [18].
Chronic renal failure	There is a link between renal failure and PAD. In <i>Heart and Estrogen/Progestin Replacement Study (HERS)</i> renal failure were associated with future cases of PAD in postmenopausal women [19].

many risk factors for the development of civilization diseases, including atherosclerosis. Equally important is the maintenance of correct eating habits, the use of appropriate proportions, the number of individual ingredients and the form of their consumption [20].

5. Symptoms of PAD

Symptoms of PAD include: symptomatic disease - Intermittent Claudication (IC) and critical lower limb ischemia. PAD may also occur as asymptomatic arterial insufficiency. In patients with peripheral arterial atherosclerosis, there is a significant reduction in physical performance and walking problems. These effects cause the PAD to limit its physical function and deteriorate the quality of life. The classic symptom of this condition is intermittent claudication, which is referred to as physical exertion in the lower limb, which passes after about 10 minutes of rest. Symptoms often appear after passing a certain distance. Patients experience muscle fatigue, stiffness, hardness, increased pain and cramps during physical activity, which gradually disappear after cessation of exercise. These symptoms are usually located in the calf area but may also affect the buttocks, thighs and feet. Termination refers to approximately 1/3 of all patients with peripheral arterial occlusion. Patients without classical shingles also have some walking limitations that may be associated with or atypical limb symptoms [3,21]. Symptoms of this condition include: changes in the skin color of the feet (pallor, bruise, lower limb elevation), discoloration, hair loss, muscular atrophy, weak or absent heart rate in the lower limb arteries and advanced healing of wounds, ulcers and necrosis of distal limbs [21]. Vascular constriction can occur at various stages. Depending on the location of the occlusion in the lower limb artery, symptoms may manifest themselves in different ways (Tab.2).

Evidence from scientific studies indicates that the progression of PAD is identical, regardless of whether or not the patient experiences symptoms. On the other hand, the incidence of chromosome symptoms is largely due to the degree of physical activity [3] and the location of lesions [13]. The incidence of this disease indicates that 7% of patients will undergo lower limb amputation, 4% will require amputation, and 16% will suffer from intermittent claudication [23]. The PAD requires antiplatelet therapy [24] and aggressive modification of risk factors, in-

cluding: smoking cessation and normalization of hyperlipidemia and hypertension [25]. In addition to the usual risk factors, there is increasing evidence that psychological aspects such as the treatment of depression and even subclinical depressive symptoms are important determinants in the treatment of patients with ischemic heart disease [26] and other vascular diseases.

6. Intermittent claudication classification

There are many classifications of claudication and limb ischemia. The most commonly used are Fontaine's Scale and Rutherford-Baker Classification (RB) [27], which are shown in Table 3. According to the Fontaine scale, patients in stage IIb, III and IV are eligible for surgical treatment. In Rutherford Classification, intermittent claudication is reported in categories 1 - 3, whereas intravascular or surgical interventions are performed in category 3 and above.

Amputation is the ultimate and rare solution in intermittent claudication. It is estimated that approximately 5.8% of patients are deprived of the lower limb for vascular causes. [29]. In case of critical limb ischaemia (Stage III and IV according to Fontaine), amputation is the only possible solution and affects part or all of the lower limb.

7. Diagnosis of intermittent claudication

Ankle-brachial index

Despite the development of imaging and technological progress, measurement of arterial pressure in the ankle region has become a standard pre-test for patients suspected of having PAD. The sphygmomanometer cuff is located just above the ankle and Doppler is used to measure the systolic pressure on the posterior and posterior artery of the foot and lower limb artery (Figure 1). However, there should be some limitation of the index for patients with impaired and non-susceptible (e.g., diabetic, renal failure) peripheral arteries to properly perform and interpret the measurement.

The readings are compared to the brachial pressure on this side, after which the measurement has higher values, resulting in ankle-brachial index (ABI). The index limb is the one with the lower ABI [3]. Systolic blood pressure at the level of the ankle should be equal to or higher than that of the brachial artery. The correct result is 0.9 - 1.15, while the ABI below 0.9 indicates the presence of stenosis. ABI above 1.3 may indicate abnormal stiffness of the vessels eg in patients with diabetes [14].

Table 2. Occurrence of symptoms depending on the localization of chronic limb artery occlusion [22].

Localization of chronic limb artery occlusion	Symptoms
Aorto-iliac (Leriche syndrome)	Intermittent claudication experienced thigh or buttocks, muscular atrophy in the legs can occur impotence
Femoro-popliteal (70% of patients)	Intermittent claudication after walking a few hundred meters
Peripheral (below the popliteal artery fork)	Occurrence of cold feeling, paraesthesia, tingling, foot pain; often coexisting with diabetes
Multilevel	Clear ischemia in various arteries, changes in limb necrosis.

Table 3. Classification of Fontaine and Rutherford based on Dormanda J.A., Rutherford R.B., for the TASC Working Group: TransAtlantic Inter-Society Consensus (TASC) [28].

FONTAINE		RUTHERFORD		
Stage	Symptoms	Stage	Category	Symptoms
I	No symptoms	0	0	No symptoms
IIa	Mild intermittent claudication	I	1	Mild intermittent claudication
IIb	Moderate-severe intermittent claudication	I	2	Moderate intermittent claudication
		I	3	Severe intermittent claudication
III	Resting ischemic pain	II	4	Resting ischemic pain
IV	Ulceration or necrosis	III	5	Slight tissue defects
		IV	6	Ulceration or necrosis

Fig. 1. Measurement of the ankle-brachial index (ABI) [30].

Functional testing using a movable treadmill

This is a comparison of the ABI at rest with the result after the effort. During a test on a moving treadmill, the patient marches at a steady speed and a constant tread of the treadmill until pain in the limb occurs or the time limit runs out. In the case of significant changes in the arteries, a significant decrease in ABI is observed in relation to the resting value [14].

Differential diagnosis of intermittent claudication

Chromatic interventions should be distinguished from alleged chlamydia, which may occur in many other pathological conditions. Patients with PAD risk, lower limb symptoms during exercise, and / or functional limitation of the limbs should be subjected to objective tests for the presence of chromosomal abnormalities and other movement limiting symptoms, since such treatment allows for proper

diagnosis and differential diagnosis of other diseases with which to differentiate (eg, narrowing of the spinal canal, hip inflammation, chronic coma of the fascia).

8. Physiotherapy and physical activity in intermittent claudication

Physical training is a good and effective method for intermittent claudication. Erb was the first to describe the beneficial effect of lower extremity blood pressure training in patients at the onset of atherosclerosis [31].

Systematic training of the lower limb muscles increases the amount of mitochondria in the muscle cells and stimulates the proliferation of blood vessels, which form the network of peripheral vascular vessels, bypassing the altered arteries. Physical exercise also reduces blood density and improves oxygen

transport in tissues. They also affect the risk factors for the development of atherosclerosis, which is the main recommendation for this disease.

There are many workout programs. Most commonly used is a program consisting of 3 sets of exercises:

- 1) 5-minute exercise warm up session,
- 2) 20-minute treadmill training (up to 90% of the maximum distance)
- 3) 20-minute ergometer exercises.

More intensive programs add 15 more minutes of ball drills. These exercises are performed twice a day for at least 12 weeks. In most patients after the training, an increase in the distance of the bladder from 50% to 200% [32].

Outpatient treatment is recommended for long-distance walking (approx. 2-3 km / day), stressing that muscular pain is not allowed. The importance of supervised physical activity as the most important component in the comprehensive treatment of patients with chronic ischemia is undisputed, as demonstrated in many clinical trials [33,34].

Unfortunately, due to accompanying diseases, especially coronary heart disease, only 25-50% of patients are able to complete a training program [35].

Conclusion

Despite many researches on the development of atherosclerosis, no one has developed an effective method to stop its progress. Only described and developed methods of treatment of risk factors for its development (hypertension, disorders of lipid and carbohydrate metabolism, obesity and others). For this reason, the greatest emphasis should be placed on primary prevention to prevent vascular changes but also secondary prevention so that existing disease does not develop.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.